

The Alchemical Writings of Nāgārjuna Siddha: Sources for a Critical Edition of the *Rasendramaṅgala*

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Figure 1: MS Ahmedabad LDI 9442 (see also Fig. 14).

1 Manuscripts consulted

1.1 Ahmedabad LDI 9442 (A₁)

Lalbbhai Dalpatbhai Institute of Indology, Ahmedabad.

Described by Puṇyavijayaḥ and Shah (1963–68: v. 4, serial #1285, accession #9442). In Āc. Vijayasevasūri’s and Āc. Kṣāntisūri’s collections. Old accession number 535.

Text and *ṭiṭpaṇa*, the latter not ascribed to anyone, but the same as that ascribed to Govindabhadra in other MSS. Library pagination 1–49. Scribal foliation 1–25. 13 lines/page, 47 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī from western India, with some *prṣṭhamātrā* vowels. Verses numbered throughout. Marginal annotations and corrections throughout. Marginal illustration of alchemical apparatus on leaf 2r, and 27 fuller illustrations on leaves 24v–25v.

Incipit, f. 1v:

śrīvaraddhamānājineśvarāya namaḥ || śrīgurubhyo namaḥ ||
 natvā sureṇdraṃ śivasaukhyadāyakaṃ ‘kāraḥkaṃ’
 apārasaṃsārasamudratāraḥkaṃ
 savarthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaṃ
 graṃthaṃ pravakṣyāmi rasendramāṅgalaṃ 1

Text ends, and *ṭiṭpaṇa* starts, ff. 19v–20r:

vyādhim ādau parikṣetaṃ tato dadyāvabheṣajam
 sūtakena samāyuktaṃ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ 22
 iti śrīmannāgārjunō viracite raseṇdraṃmaṅgale
 guṭikātvādutijalūkājaraṇādirasa[f. 20r]baṃdhanam nāma caturtho
 dhyāyaḥ 4

Abbreviations: **biw-bibl** = Biswas and Prajapati (1998), **meul-hist** = Meulenbeld (1999), **ncc** = Raghavan, Kunjunni Raja, Sundaram, et al. (1949).

Ṭippaṇa begins, f. 20r:

om namaḥ
pītāṃbaro ghalijimnāgakṣayabahalarāgagaruḍacaraḥ
sa jayati hariva harijovidalitabhavadainyuduḥ'hara'
saptaviṃśatisiddhānām matam ālokya yatnataḥ 2

Ṭippaṇa ends, ff. 23v–24r:

raktaprāvaraṇākam guṇī naravahāruvarāṭakaḥ grahagodhā
svetapallīvisambhāro
iti raseṃdramamgale [f. 24r] ṭṭipāṇakam samāptam

= MS A₂ f. 95v

Then immediately begins the *Loharasāyana* declared by Nāgārjuna, that according to the explicit is also included in the *Rasendramaṅgala*:

vakṣe nāgārjunaproktam lohasyaiva rasāyanam

Explicit, f. 24v:

vāṃgerīsvāṃganiryāsaiḥ rathena vidhinā caret
taṃduliyakamūlasya rasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ 8
iti śrīmannāgārjunō viracitāyām raseṃdramamgalaṃ sampūrṇam ||

sakalapuṃḍitasumanah svāmipamḍitaśrī 5
śrīvarddhamānavimalagaṇīśīṣyāṇuḥ ratanavimala lakhitam
śrīmaddahimadāvādanagare nakare śrīkālupure saṃvat 1737 varṣe
māgha śudi 6 śanau paropakārāya vācanārtham lipikṛtam asti ||
yādr̥ṣam pustake dr̥ṣtam tādr̥ṣam likhitam mayā
yadi śuddham aśuddham vā mama doṣo na dīyatām 1
śrīr astuḥ kalyāṇam astuḥ śubham bhavatuḥ śreyo stuḥ sakalasajjanasya
śrīr astuḥ [Followed by annotated illustrations.]

I.e., copied by the scribe Ratnavimala, pupil of Varddhamāna Vimalagaṇī, in Ahmedabad, at Kālupura, on Saturday 6 śuklapakṣa of Māgha, saṃ 1737, i.e., AD 1681.

1.2 Ahmedabad, LDI 7753 (A₂)

Lalbbhai Dalpatbhai Institute of Indology, Ahmedabad.

Described by Puṇyavijayajī and Shah (1963–68: v. 2, 830–831, #6498).

The text with the *ṭippaṇa* of Govindabhadra. Leaves 3–66, 70–78, 90–95. 9 lines/page, 25 akṣaras/line of large Devanāgarī. Numbered verses throughout.

Incipit, f. 3r with verse i. 17:

16 sarvauvyadhānām [sic] kṛtayogam ekataḥ sasthai'cha'lvapalvair
varayogaratnaiḥ
na yāti tulyam naranāthabhūtale raseṃdrayogāc chatakoṭīraṃśataḥ 17

F. 33v has end of adhyāya 3:

Figure 2: MS Ahmedabad LDI 7753 (A2).

iti śrīśrīnanāgārjunaviracite raseṁdramamṅgale
 bhasmasūtakaprabodonāma tṛtīyo 'dhyāyaḥ 3 athāto guṭīkādhikāraṁ
 vyākhyāsyāmo cayam śubham sadā

F. 44r has the verse 4.212 (*RM_{ed}*: 169) followed by two additional verses and a scribal mark indicating missing akṣaras. The text then continues in the middle of the verse beginning “*śulvam api pakvaṁ.*” The manuscript thus omits an important transition to the first verses of the *Kakṣaputa* section. See Fig. 3.

F. 49r has:

śrīśailaparvatastho sau siddo nāgārjjuno mahān sarvasatvopakārī ca
 sarvabhogaguṇānvitaḥ 54

F. 62r has:

vyādhim ādau parīkṣyeta tato dadyāc ca bheṣajam
 sūtakenasamāyuktaṁ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ 114
 iti śrī śrīmannāgārjunaviracite raseṁdramamṅgale
 guṭīkāsatvadrutijalūkājāraṇādirasabaṁdhanam nāma caturtho dhyāya 4
 | *

Ṭippaṇa begins:

śrīgaṇāpataye namaḥ
 atha raseṁdramamṅgalasya ṭikā liṣyate
 śaṁvaro 'tha balijinnāgakṣa[f. 62v]yabahalarāgagaruḍacaraḥ
 sa jayati harir iva harajo vidalitabhavadainyaduḥkhaharaḥ 1
 saptāvīṁśatisiddhānā matam ālokya yatnataḥ ...
 paramahaṁsaparivrājākācāryabhagatpūjyapādam aṣṭāvīṁśatimam
 rasisiddham śrī śrīmadGovīṁdabhadrākhyo 'haṁ raseṁdramamṅgalasya
 ṭippaṇam racayāmi 5

Figure 3: MS Ahmedabad LDI 7753 (A2), f. 44r.

70v has:

iti śodhanaprakaraṇaṃ

71r has:

atha mahārasaśodhanam

Explicit, f. 95v:

raktaprāvaraṇā | kaṃguṇī | maṭa --- raṭhakaḥ | grhagodhā |
 śvetaviśambhakaḥ | *
 iti raseṃdramamgale ṭṭipāṇakaṃ saṃpūrṇaṃ samāptaṃ || saṃvat 1837
 varṣe māghamāse śuklapakṣe dvitīyāyāṃ tithau bhṛaguvāse
 hamīrapurama_dhye ṣerāmarāmasyātmapasukharāmeṇedaṃ pustakaṃ
 samaliṣita śubhaṃ bhūyāt kalyāṇam astu || śrīr astu

= MS A1 f. 23v

I.e., copied by the scribe Sukharāma, son of Kherāmarāma, in Hammīrapura, on Thursday 2 śuklapakṣa of Māgha, saṃ 1837, i.e., CE 1780.

1.3 Bikaner Anup 4281 (V₁)

Anup Sanskrit Library, Lallgarh Palace, Bikaner.

The Bikaner (Sanskrit Vikramapura) MS, housed in the Anup Library, was unavailable to me. The owners of the Anup Library do not cooperate with scholars.

Described by Raja, Chittenjoor Kunhan, and Sarma, K Madhava Krishna (1944), *Catalogue of the Anup Sanskrit Library. Bikaner* (Government Press), URL: <https://archive.org/details/b32882099>, accessed 09/09/2022: 328, #4281.

The text transmitted in this manuscript can be reconstructed from the two known apographs, one in Paris and another in London.

Figure 4: MS Paris BNF Cordier 1222.

Paris BNF Cordier 1222 (P)

Bibliothèque Nationale, Paris. The library has made available [a scan of this MS](#).

Described by Cordier (1903: 347–8). This is an apograph of V₁.

Based on this manuscript, Cordier (1903) described the *Rasendramaṅgala* as follows:

The *Rasendramaṅgala* of Siddha Nāgārjuna, having 8 adhikāras of which we only possess the first four, accompanied by an anonymous *ṭippanī*, is confused with the *Rasaratnākara* recently used by Prof. P. C. Rāy for his *History of Indian Chemistry*, according to a damaged copy from the library in Jammu. Our MS, the second known, is at once more correct and better preserved. Chapter 4 deserves our special attention because, amongst other unedited circumstances, it shows us Siddha Nāgārjuna on mount Śrī Śaila (or Śrīparvata); Wassilieff, *Bouddh.* p. 203, 326), teaching the doctrines of alchemy to 50 people amongst which number Ratnaghoṣa and Śūrasena (cf. *Rasaratnasamuccaya*), invoking a *Vaṭayakṣiṇī* by means of tradition invocations, and finally engaging with the king, Śālivāhana, who declares that he will sacrifice to the great art, “his gold, his jewels, his treasures, his own person, and his royal wife Madasundarī.”

Further on, the legend is told of Māṇḍavya, who succeeded in preparing gold by means of red copper, iron, lead and yellow copper, and by whom *Vaśiṣṭa* was taught about metallurgical operations. After a short account of the śāstra entitled *Vaśiṣṭamāṇḍavya* and of the treatise of *Mārkaṇḍeya*, the chapter finishes with a dialogue between Nāgārjuna and Ratnaghoṣa. It is thus clear that the authorship of the *Rasendramaṅgala* cannot reasonably be attributed to Nāgārjuna himself; the work, whose author we do not yet know, looks distinctly Buddhist (“*maitrikaruṇā’pekṣā sarvasattveṣu*”; “*uṣṇīṣarakṣābaliḥ...*” etc.), and mentions the physician

Nāgabuddhi (Sē Rasaratnasa., and Wassilieff, loc. cit.). If one recalls that the tantra called Subāhupariṣcchāsūtra, studied by Wassilieff (p. 190–199), includes the creation of gold and the transmutation of earth into gold amongst the eight siddhis, and that a translation of this text into Chinese was made between 265 and 316 A. D. (Nanjio, col. 25, no. 49), one must admit that the origins of Indian alchemy go back without question much further than was admitted generally before the publication of P. C. Ray’s work.

Also described by Filliozat (1934: 161, #146): “Rasendramaṅgala, par Nāgārjuna, avec commentaire, 39 fol., incomplet.”

Leaves 1–35. 10 lines/page, 50 akṣaras/line of clear modern Devanāgarī. Most verses unnumbered. Parts of the MS have numerous interlinear corrections in Devanāgarī and Roman script, presumably by Cordier. Covers the text followed by a *ṭippaṇa*.

F. 1r has:

śrī vikramapurarājapustakālaye || pu° nam° 1506 || de° || pa° 38 ||
rasam° || 74 na° 1506 śrī nāgārjjunakṛtam rasendramaṅgalam || | p° 38

Incipit, f. 1v:

|| śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ || ||
natvā sureṣṇḍram ‘sureṣṇḍram’ śivasaukhyadāyakam |

Śrīśaila passage covers ff. 25r–29v.

Text ends, f. 30r:

śrīmannāgārjunaviracite raseṣṇḍramaṅgale guṭikākhye
druṭijalūkāmāraṇādirasabaṃdhanam nāma caturtho dhyāyah | 4 |

Ṭippaṇa begins, f. 30r:

om namaḥ śivāya ||
pītāṃbaro gha ‘tha’balijinnāgakṣayabahalarāgagaruḍacarah |
sa jayati hariva hari’ra’jo vidalitabhavadainyaduḥkhaharah

Explicit, f. 35v:

cāmgerīsvāṃganiryāsaiḥ rathainaṃ vidhinā caret |
taṃḍulīyakamūlasya rasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ || ||
iti śrīmannāgārjjuno viracitāyāṃ raseṣṇḍramaṅgalam samāptam || ||
saṃvat 1956 kārttikaśukla 15 bhṛgubāsare || śubham bhūyāt || lipikṛtam
prohitadīnanāthenedam pustakam || ||

I.e., copied by Purohita Dīnanātha in Vikramapura (Bikaner) on Thursday 15 śuklapakṣa of Kārttika, saṃ 1956, i.e., AD 1899.

The manuscript contains numerous interlinear notes and corrections in a modern hand. These appear to be by Cordier and to follow MS Jammu Raghunātha 3153 (R) (see section 1.11 below).

London Wellcome (L)

A scribe from Bikaner, hired by me in 1984–85, made a useful hand copy of MS Bikaner Anup 4281, copies of which are now in the library of the Wellcome Institute for the History of Medicine, in London and in my personal possession.

It covers the text followed by a *vyākhyāna*.

Leaves 1–78, written on one side only of machine made foolscap paper. 25 lines/page, 27 akṣaras/line of modern Devanāgarī handwriting, using ballpoint pen. Most verses unnumbered. Corrections throughout in red ballpoint. Pages 35, 36 in a different hand.

Incipit, f. 1:

śrī gaṇeśāya namaḥ
natvā
suresendraṃ śivasaukhyadāyakaṃ |
apārasaṃsārasamudratārakaṃ
sarvārtha-
siddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaṃ |
graṃthaṃ
pravakṣyāmi rasendramāṅgalaṃ |

Śrīśaila passage covers pp. 49–59.
Text ends, f. 61:

sūvakena samāyuktaṃ
yojayec ca bhīṣagvaraḥ |
śrīmannāgārjunaviracite
rasendramāṅgale guṭikātve-
druṭijalūkājāraṇādirasabamḍhanaṃ
nāma caturtho 'dhyāyaḥ |

Ṭippana begins, f. 62:

oṃ namaḥ śivāyaḥ |
pītāṃbaro dhavalijin-
nāgakṣayavahalarāgagaruḍacaraḥ |
sa jayati urava harijo
vidalitabhavadainyaduḥkhaharaḥ ||

F. 63 has:

nāgārjunasurāvido nāgabodhir
yaśodharaḥ |
ṣaṃḍakapālīko brahmā govido
laṃpako hariḥ |
saptaviṃśatibhūpeṃdrā
rasasiddhāḥ prakīrtitā |
eteṣāṃ matam ālokya yatnena
paramādade |
deṣe deṣe nānā ūśadhānāṃ
dhātūnāṃ ca pṛthak kṛtvā drṣṭvā

Figure 5: MS London Wu-
jastyk, apograph of Bikaner
Anup 4281.

pāraṃparyeṇa
rasendramaṅgalagraṃthasya
vyākhyānaṃ karomi |
natvā rasendraśivasaukhyakārakam
...

Explicit, f. 78:

taṃḍulīpakamūlasya rasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ ||
iti śrīmannāgārjuno viracitāyāṃ raseṃdramaṅgala samāptam | śrīr
astuḥ || kalyāṇam astuḥ |

1.4 Bombay BBRAS S.C.19/2 (B)

Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society, Mumbai, Maharashtra.

Described by Velankar (1925–30: appendix B, p. 494).

The outside cover of the manuscript is marked “S. C. $\frac{19}{2}$.” Text and *ṭippaṇa*.
The latter is ascribed to Govindacandra and is incomplete.

Leaves 2–24. 15 lines/page, 60 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī from western India, with pṛṣṭhamātrā vowels. Verses numbered throughout. Illustrations on ff. 20v–21v.

Incipit, f. 2r:

je kathayate vidyaḥ || 18
malena mūrcchāṃ śikhinā ca dādya’ho’ viṣeṇa mrtyu pravadaṃti samtaḥ
gurutvadoṣeṇa karoti śūlaṃ na tiṣṭhate taccapalatvadoṣāt || 19

F. 3v:

||57|| iti śrīnāgārjunaviracita raseṃdramaṅgale
rasoparasalohaḥ bodhaḥ bhikādhikāraḥ prathamah||cha|| || athato

F. 5r:

śodhanaṃ|| cha || iti śrīnāgārjunaviracita raseṃdramaṅgale
satvapātanasyābhṛakādīdrutidrāvaṇavajramohamāraṇādhikāro dvitīyaḥ||
cha|| athato

F. 10v, line 6, has:

|| 46 rasavarttinetraroge ||
vyoṣaṃtri aṃjanaṃ śunthaṃ kūnaṭi siṃdhusaimdhavaṃ |
vimalāsthi śītalaṃ sūtaṃ ajākṣīreṇa pīṣayet || 47
nāśayet timiraṃ kācaṃ paṭalaṃ arbuḍaṃ tathā
adhikāni tu māṃsāni yasya dūra na paśyati || 48
iti netrarogarasayogyāḥ || cha|| gagana...

F. 11r has:

iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite raseṃdramaṅgale bhasmasūtakaprabādho nāma
tṛtīyo dhyāyaḥ|| cha || || atha guṭikā|| pūrve yanmāritam ...

F. 14r:2 has:

23 praṇipatya sarvabuddhān sakaladoṣavimuktān | vakṣyai sarvvaṃ
hitārthaṃ kakṣāpuṣasarvasiddhikaraṃ | 24 gaṃdha <lb/> kadaradaśilā
lormmāksīkāsīsatāthyagirikayā | samsthāpya madhya koṣṭe
vyomāsītahemavīrṇarasayuktān || 25

F. 15r has:

śrīśīlaparvatastho siddho nāgārjuno mahān || 79 sarvasatvopakārī ca
sarvaṭṅguṇānvitah |

Text ends f. 18v:

vyādhinādaḥ prarīkṣeta tato dadyāc ca bhiṣajaṃ svatakena samāyuktaṃ
yojayec ca bhiṣagvara || 22
iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale
guṭīkāsatvadrutijalūkājāraṇādirasabaṃdhano nāma caturthādhyāyaḥ |
samāptaḥ || * ||

Ṭippaṇa begins, f. 18v:

oṃ namo gaṇapataye ||
pītāṃbaro tha valijinnāgakṣayavahalarāgagaruḍavaraḥ |
sa jayati harir iva harajo vidali | tabhavadaityaduḥkhaharaḥ || 1
saptaviṃśatisiddhānā matam āṃlokya yatnataḥ |
nānā śāstranighaṇṭhāni jñātvādaḥ vaidyakatrayaṃ || 2 ... racayāmi
karttāhaṃ paramahaṃsaparivrājakācāryabhagavatpūjyapādam
aṣṭaviṃśatimaṃ rasasiddhiṃ śrīmadGovīṃdacaṃdrākhyam kiṃ tata
ṭṭippaṇakaṃ syād rasendramaṅgalaś ca
rasendramaṅgalābhīdhānagraṃthaś ca susaṃvedeṣu gūḍhārthasya |

Leaves 20v–21r have 29 diagrams of alchemical yantras.

Explicit, f. 24v:

miti | vadarī † paca † ṇi vāyamūṣeti | vaṭavālāraktāṃkuraṃ | pavāṃtrīṇi
vāṭayitvā madhye hīrā † ścāpyavā [*Text breaks off.*]

1.5 Jaipur UIOMI 184: I.14.ii.2 (J₁)

The Universal Institute of Orientology and Museum of Indology, Prachya-Vidya-Path, 24 Gangwal Park, Jaipur, Rajasthan.

Described by SRCPVPS Trust (1986: 63). Text and anonymous *ṭippaṇa*. Leaves 1–43, 46–48, 51. 13 lines/page, 35 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī. Some verses numbered. Some marginal annotations and corrections. Illustrations of alchemical apparatus on ff. 41r–42v.

Ff. 1–8 of this MS are from another work, but copied in the same hand as the whole MS.

Begins, f. 1v:

Śrīśaila passage covers ff. 31v–39r.

Text ends, ff. 38v–39r:

vyādhim ādau parikṣe[f. 39r] tato dadyā ca bheṣaja
sūtakena samāyuktaṃ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ

iti śrīmannāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale
guṭikātvēdutijalūkājāraṇādirasavaṃdhanam nāma caturtho dhyāyaḥ

Ṭippaṇa begins, f. 39r:

oṃ namaḥ śivāya
pītāṃvarthavalijinnāgakṣayaḥ bahalarāgī garuḍavaraḥ
sa jayati hariva harajo vidalītabhavadaitya duḥkhaharaḥ 1
saptaviṃśatisiddhānā matam ālokya yatnataḥ 2

Explicit, f. 51v:

cāṃgerīsvāṃganiryāsaiḥ rathaiḥ naṃ vidhinā caret
taṃdulīyakamūlasya rasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ
iti śrīmannāgārjunō viracitāyāṃ rasendramaṅgalaṃ samāptaḥ||
śrīr astu kalyāṇam astu śrī

1.6 Udaipur IRS 1136 (U)

The Institute of Rajasthan Studies, Rājasthāna Vidyāpīṭha, Udaipur, Rajasthan.

Described by Paliwal (1978: 164, #1136).

Text and anonymous *ṭippaṇa*. Leaves 1–43. 9 lines/page, 46 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī. Verses numbered throughout. Some interlinear annotations and corrections.

No illustrations, and no *ṭippaṇa*. Notably clear hand.

Incipit, f. 1v:

śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ|| rasendrāya namaḥ||
oṃ
natvā narasendram śivasaukhyakāraṃkaṃ
apārasaṃsārasaśū‘mū‘dratāraṃkaṃ|
sarvārthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaṃ
graṃthaṃ pravakṣyāmi rasendramaṅgalaṃ | 1 |

F. 8v has:

iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale vajramāraṇasatvapātana
abhakādi drutidrāvaṇalohamāraṇādhikāraḥ dvitīyaḥ//2// // athato
rasavaṃdhanādhikāraṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ//

F. 22r has:

iti śrīmannāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale bhasmasūtakaṃ//
prabādhānāmma tṛtīyo dhyāyaḥ//3// // atha guṭikādhikāraḥ
prārabhyate//

Figure 7: MS Goṇḍal BP 34 (G).

F. 24r has:

iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasendramamṅgale guṭikādhikāro nāma
caturthaḥ//4// punar anyam pravakṣyāmi prayogaṃ bhuvī durlabham//

Text ends, ff. 43v:

vidhim ādau parikṣeta tato dadyāc ca bheṣajam ||
sūtakena samāyuktaṃ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ ||
iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasendramamṅgale
guṭikāsatvadrutijalūkājāraṇādirasabaṃdhanam nāma caturtho dhyāyaḥ||
śrīkalyāṇam astu|| śrī|| śrī|| śrī||

1.7 Goṇḍal BP 34 (G)

Gujarat Ayurveda University Library, Jamnagar, Gujarat. Formerly in the Rasaśāstraśadhālaya and Bhuvaneśvarīpīṭha Library of Jīvarāma Kālidāsa Śāstri in Goṇḍal, Gujarat.

MS (Fig. 7) is described by Śāstri (1960: 26, serial no 34). The catalogue records the date of copying the MS as saṃ 1996 (CE 1939/40), and the number of leaves as 37. The late date of copying suggests that Jīvarāma Kālidāsa Śāstri, who assembled the Goṇḍal MS collection, may have had the manuscript copied for his library from another extant copy.

The whole of the Śrī Bhuvaneśvarī Pīṭha Goṇḍal MS collection was transferred to The Gujarat Ayurvedic University, Jamnagar, in about 1970, and is now housed there in the university library block.

The manuscript was inspected briefly during a visit to Jamnagar in 1991, and a photocopy was received in early 1993. The manuscript does not include drawings or *ṭippaṇa*.

Digital images of the manuscript have since become available as downloads from the GAU website.¹

Ff. 1–37, 12 lines/page, 34 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī.
Begins, f. 1r:

śrī gaṇeśāya namaḥ ||
atha rasendramaṅgalo nāmā graṃto likhyate ||
natvā sureṃdraṃ śivasaukhyadāyakaṃ
apārasaṃsārasamudratāraṃ
sarvārthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaṃ
graṃthaṃ pravakṣyāmi rasendramaṅgalaṃ || 1||

F. 29r:9 has:

rājikārdhamātreṇa parvvatān api vidhyati// atha kakṣapuṭaṃ/ śrīḥ
praṇipatya sarvvabuddhān sakaladoṣe nirmuktā siddhān// vakṣye
sarvvaḥitārthaṃ kakṣapuṭaṃ sarvasiddhikaraṃ/ gaṃdhaka
tharaha†śilālaiḥ kāmḥkṣikāsīsātāpyagairikaṃ// saṃsthāpya
madhyakoṣṭhe vyomāsitaḥmacīṃarasayuktān/ ...

F. 31v has:

tad ahaṃ pravakṣyāmi sādhanam ca yathāvidhiḥ/ satvānām
bodhanāthayisādhitā vaṭayakṣiṇī// mayā dvādaśavarṣāṇi soḍhaḥ kleśo
mahānetattu// tatkāle dṛṣṭa divyānām divyāvācā mayā śrutā//

F. 33v has, last line:

dviguṇaṃ yadi kartavyaṃ pūrvasaṃskāram uttamaṃ// triguṇaṃ ca
bhavedbaṃdhaḥ kramakrameṇa yojitaṃ// śrīr astu

Ends, f. 37v:

yasya rāgasya yo yogas tena vai sahayojayet||
rasendro harate vyādhiṃ narakuṃjaravājinām||
iti śrīmannāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale
guṭikāsatvadrutijalūkājāraṇādirasabaṃdhano nāma caturtho 'dhyāyaḥ||
śubhaṃ bhūyāt|| graṃthāgraṃ 960|| śrīḥ

1.8 Patan HJ 8930 (Pa)

Śrī Hemacandrācārya Jainajñānamandira, Pāṭan, Śrī Sāgara Gacchano Jaina Jñānabhaṃdāra collection.

MS described in Puṇyavijayajī (1972: 329–435, #8930).

Address for correspondence: Mayur Shah, 10 Bharati Society, Patan 384265, India.

Ff. 1v–21v, 20 lines/page, 60 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī. Missing ff. 4–9. I.e., with the missing ff. (4–9) it would have been approximately 1538 granthas in length.

¹<http://www.ayurvedamanuscripts.com/>, consulted May 2013.

Description
unfinished

F. 1v has the marginal note in roman script: “Some where the folios are very dull in Prata and folio no. 4–9 are missing in original Prata. “

Begins, f. 1r:

||siddham|| om̐ namo rasem̐drāya gurubhyo namaḥ||
natvā rasem̐draṃ śivasaukhyakāraṃ/
apārsamsārasamudratāraṃ/
sarvārthasiddhipradamukhymaṅgelaṃ/
graṃthaṃ pravakṣyāmi rasem̐dramaṅgalaṃ// 1//

F. 2v has:

iti nāgārjunaviracite rasem̐dramaṅgale rasoparasnalohaśodhanādhikāraḥ
prathamaḥ athāto vajrādau lohamāraṇadhānyādhikāra vyākhyāsyāmaḥ

F. 3v has:

iti śrīmannāgārjunaviracite rasem̐dramaṅgale vajrabhāraṇasatvapātana
abhrakādidrutidrāvaṇalohamāraṇādhikāro dvitīyaḥ// 2// cha// athato
rasabaṃdhādhikāraṃ vyākhyāsyāmaṃ/
jaṃbīranīranavasāraghanāmlavargaḥ...

F. 3v breaks off at ch. 3:4b of *RM_{ed}*: 49, exactly before the Prajñāpāramitā verse.
There is a lacuna here from the beginning to the middle of chapter four.

F. 10r begins,

tu jāyate / lāṃgalīkaravīraṃ ca

which is ch. 4:68 of *RM_{ed}*: 133.

F. 14r has,

śrīsailaḥ parvatastho sau siddo nāgārjuno mahān
sarvasattvopakārī ca sarvabhogaguṇānvitaḥ /
pārthito dadhate śīghraṃ yasya yasya hi yādṛśaṃ ‘75’

I.e., the beginning of the Śrīsaila passage.

F. 17v has,

yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ//
iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasem̐dramaṅgale
guṭīkātveprutijalūkājāraṇādirasabaṃdhanam̐ nāma caturtho
dhyāyaḥ// 4//
om̐ namaḥ śivāya/
pītāṃbaro dhavalijinnnāgākṣayabahalarāgaruḍacaraḥ /
sa jayati harir iva ...

I.e., the end of chapter 4 and the start of the commentary.

F. 21v:3 has,

iti rasem̐dramaṅgale tippanakaṃ samāptaṃ/ vakṣe nāgārjjuna proktaṃ/
lohasyaivarasāvaṃ/

Ends, f. 21v, last line:

tanduliyakamūlasvarasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ||
iti śrīmannāgārjunaviracitaṃ rasem̐dramagaḥ samāpta||

Figure 8: Kobatirth Library Stamp (MS Koba GB 19113 (Ko₁), f. 1r)

1.9 Koba GB 0019113 (Ko₁)

Acharya Shri Kailasasagarasuri Gyanmandir, Shri Mahavir Jain Aaradhana Kendra, Koba, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

The Gyanbhandar Library at Koba (<http://www.kobatirth.org>) is, I believe, the largest manuscript library in the world, containing over a quarter of a million manuscripts.

The library kindly provided me with a digital copy of the manuscript, called HP_AA_19113_300DPI.pdf. The staff at the Koba library were extraordinarily kind, efficient and helpful.

Ff. 1v–29v, 15 lines/page, 41 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī. 1095 granthas in length.

Begins, f. 1v:

||siddhaṃ|| śrīgaṇeśāyanamaḥ||
natvā sureśendraṃ śivasaukhyadāyakam
apārasaṃsārasamudratārakam
sarvārthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaṃ
graṃthaṃ pravakṣyāmi rasendramaṅgalaṃ

F. 19r:

nāgārjunovācaḥ
sādhu sādhu mahāprājña tuṣṭo haṃ bhaktivatsalaḥ kathayāmi na
saṃdeho yatvayā pariṛchitaṃ

F. 20v:

athātaḥ saṃpravakṣyāmi karttarirasabaṃdha[21r]naṃ uparatnāni
saṃgr̥hya bhūmaśailalatodbhavaṃ

F. 21r:

nāgārjunovācaḥ kathayāmi na saṃdeho mārttaṃḍa yena yat kṛtaṃ
dīrghāyuṣkara bhūmo rasasiddhe rasāyane

Description
unfinished

For Private And Personal Use Only

Figure 9: MS Koba GB 26264 (Ko₂), f. 1r.

F. 23r:

iti śrī nāgārjuno viracite mahāraṇuktāṣecara baṃdha samāptaḥ rase
vīrye vipāke ca śuddhaṃ ...

F. 23v:

iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite raseṃdramamaṅgale
guṭikātvedrutijalūkaājāraṇādirasabamḍhanāma caturtho dhyāyaḥ 4
oṃ namaḥ śivāyaḥ
pītāṃbaro gavalijinnāgakṣayavahanalarāgagaruḍacaraḥ
sa jayati harivaharijo vidalitabhavadainyaduḥkharahaḥ
saptaviṃśati siddhānāṃ matam ālokya yatnataḥ
nānā śāstranighaṃṭādi jñātvādaṃ vedyakatrayaṃ
deṣe deṣe bhidhānaṃ yad ośadhānāṃ pṛthak pṛthak
taṃ viditvā ca dhātūnāṃ pāraṃparyo svadeśataḥ
sāśaṃsa yasya gūḍhārthaspaṣṭhīkaraṇahetave
raseṃdramamaṅgalesyedaṃ ṭīpaṇaṃ ca racayāmy ahaṃ

Ends, f. 29v:

dharmmadhāraṇapoṣaṇe
cāṃgerīsvāṃganiryāsaiḥ rathainaṃ vidhinā caret
taṃḍulīyakamūlasyarasenāpi tataḥ punaḥ
iti śrīmannāgārjuno viracitāyāṃ raseṃdramamaṅgalaṃ samāptaṃḥ|| ||śrīr
astuḥ|| ||kalyāṇam astuḥ|| ||śubhaṃ bhavatu||

1.10 Koba GB 26264 (Ko₂)

Acharya Shri Kailasagarasuri Gyanmandir, Shri Mahavir Jain Aaradhana
Kendra, Koba, Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

३१५३	रसरत्नाकरः	नागाजुनः	...	४३	९११८	...	असंपूर्ण आरम्भान्ताभावात् । नवीना का- श्मीरिकी लिपिः ।
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Figure 10: MS Jammu Raghunātha 3153 entry in Stein 1894: 187.

Ff. 1r–5v, 13 lines/page, 36 akṣaras/line of Devanāgarī.

The library kindly provided me with a digital copy of the manuscript, called HP_AA_26264_300DPI .pdf.

Begins, f. 1r:

atha nāgārjūnakṛtarasaratnākaraṭsya ca[tu]rtho adhyāya prārabhyate śrī
sīla parvatasyotpā ṭsidho nāgārjūno mähān sarvasatvopakāri ca
sarvabhogagūṇānvīta 1
prārthanād davateśīghraḥ yasya sasyāhiyādṛsaḥ dṛṣṭvātyāgaṃ ca
sutakasyaḥ prabhāvena tathaiva ca 2
sarvasatvamāhābedhiḥ sūranasya tathaiva caḥ teṣyāṃ madhe
epradhānaṃ ca ratnaghoso prabhākara 3
kṛtāmjalī puṭo bhūtvā nāgārjunapurasthītaḥ pṛchate rasyakarmāṇi
vidyādānaṃdadāsvame 4
nāgārjunovāca sādhu sādhu mahānāgaḥ tuṣṭo hoam bhaktivachala
kathayāmi na saṃdeho ytvayā paripṛchitaṃ 5

Ends, f. 5r:

bhairavo vāca sahasraṃ pūskaraṃ ghoraṃ yadbhūtaṃ tce kṣīnaṃ tvayā
tvadbhaktiyā tū svahaṃ tuṣṭo svachāṃdapratikāraka 27
sādhuḥ mahāprājña na māmasyaśca sadhavāsvotiṣṭe ciraṃ kālāṃ
yācaṃdrā'rkatāraka 28
rudrakaṃṭhnyā vāṣṭūkāṃnyā brahmakanyā tathaiva ca bhūktāsvavipulān
bhogān kaṃnyāte mūktībhājanaṃ 28
itī nāgārjuna sadavāstraṣṭumahārasavratākṛṣṭaṣecarakoṣaṭ smāptaṃ

MS Ko₂ supports just the Śrīśaila section of the *Rasendramaṅgala*, which it calls chapter four of the *Rasaratnākara*. The same text is found in MS G (f. 27) and others in the section sometimes titled “*Kakṣapuṭam*.”

1.11 Jammu Raghunātha 3153 (R)

Raghunātha Temple Library and Dharmarth Trust, Jammu, Jammu and Kashmir.

This manuscript is noted as number 3153 in Stein’s catalogue of the Raghunātha Temple library, Jammu under the name *Rasaratnākara* (Stein 1894: 187, #3153). The work is ascribed to the author Nāgārjuna. See Fig. 10.

A scan of the MS is available at <ark:/13960/t9k41rw7f>.

Pandit Project: entiaity/110462/manuscript.

History of the manuscript

Brief extracts from this manuscript that were cited by Rây, together with a translation of the extracts², suggest that this manuscript was copied from a mixture of leaves from the *Rasaratnākara* of Nityanātha Siddha, and a different text called *Rasendramaṅgala*, as well as the *Kakṣapuṭatantra* also ascribed to Nāgārjuna Siddha.³

This manuscript is historiographically important because the enthusiastic remarks based on it and published by Rây at the start of the twentieth century misled and confused almost all twentieth-century scholars who wrote about Indian alchemy.⁴ Central to the confusion was the false idea that there existed a text called the *Rasaratnākara* by an author called Nāgārjuna. In fact, there exists a *Rasendramaṅgala* by Nāgārjuna Siddha and a *Rasaratnākara* by Nityanātha Parvatīputra.⁵

Correspondence with the authorities of the Raghunātha Temple Library and the Dharmārtha Trust in the 1990s about this manuscript resulted in some preliminary notes on the text, kindly provided by Mr K. C. Yogi of the Raghunātha Temple Library, confirming it to be a mixture of *Rasendramaṅgala* and *Rasaratnākara* leaves.

Thanks to the remarkable photographic project “eGangotri” of Mr Chetan Pandey, a high-quality digital image of this manuscript became available in 2015, under the name “Ras Ratnakar Alm 14 Shlf 3 3153 Devanagari Shri Nagarjuna,” and can now be publicly consulted at [Archive.org](https://archive.org).

Outer library label reads (see Fig. 11):

Shri Raghunath Temple MSS. Library, JAMMU.
No. 3153
Title rasa ratnākaraḥ
Author śrī nāgārjunah
Extent 43 Age x
Subject cikitsā śāstram

Manuscript begins, first unnumbered folio:

rasaratnākaraḥ
3153
3153 F.1+43 = 44
Complete

Second unnumbered folio, recto:

3153 F.1+43 = 44
Complete

²Rây 1902–09: v. 2, 1–9, appendix 3–17.

³Wujastyk 1984: 76 et passim.

⁴Including, e.g., the important remarks by Filliozat (1940; 1969) and Wieger (1922), whom he cites.

⁵Wujastyk (1984) gives an account of this confusion. There is, in fact, a small amount of fluidity in manuscript colophons, and Rây was unlucky to have based his interesting scholarship on a manuscript with misleading colophons.

Figure 11: Label of MS Jammu Raghunātha 3153.

rasaratnākaraḥ nāgārjunaviracitaḥ
 rasasāra
 aṅkā 3153

Verso contains a table of contents beginning with 1 *mahārasaśodhanaṃ*, ending 43 *sārasuṃdarorasaḥ*.

First foliated leaf begins, f. 1v:

om śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ|| atha mahārasaśodhanaṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ
 kimadra citraṃ yadi rājavartakaṃ śirīṣapuṣpāgrarasena bhāvitam
 sitaṃ suvarṇaṃ taruṇārkaśannibhaṃ karoti guṃjāśatam ekaguṃjajā

This passage corresponds to *Rasendramaṅgala* 1.40, especially in MS A₂.

F. 3v has:

iti nāgārjunaviracite rasaratnākare rasoparasaśodhananā[mā]dhikāraḥ
 prathamaḥ meṣaśrīngatujamgāca

F. 7r has:

vajramāraṇasatvapātarābhṛakādīdrutidrāvaṇavajralohamāraṇādhi-
 kāro nāma dvitīyaḥ
 athāto rasabandhādihikāraṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ
 jambīraje navasāra

F. 20r has:

iti śrīnāgārjunaviracite rasaratnākare bhasmasūtakaprabandho nāma
 tṛtīyodhikāraḥ//

F. 28v:9 begins:

śrīśailaparvatasthāyī siddho nāgārjuno mahān
sarvasatvopakārī ca sarvabhāgyasamā[f. 29r]nvataḥ
prārthito dadate śīghraṃ tenāpaśya hi yādṛśaṃ
dṛṣṭvā tyāgaṃ ca bhogaṃ ca sūtakasya prasādataḥ
sarvasatvamayo vedhī svarasenas tathaiva ca
teṣāṃ madhyo pradānaṃ ca ratnaghoṣapratāraḥ
kṛtāmjali puṭobhūtvā nāgārjunapurasthitaḥ
pṛśchate rasakanyāni vidyādānaṃ dadasva me//

śrī nāgārjuna uvāca
sādhu sādhu mahāmnājñā tuṣṭoḥaṃ bhaktivatsala
kathayāmi na mande hoyattvayā paripṛśchātāṃ
valīpālitanāśaṃ ca tathākālasya vāṃcanaṃ
yathā lohe tathā dehe kṣamate nātra saṃśayaḥ
sahasrāsavalatvaṃ ca kodivedhībhaveḍ rasaḥ
tad ahaṃ saṃpravakṣāmi bhavato hi yathāvidhi
satvānāṃ bhojanārthāya sādhitā vaṭayakṣiṇī
dvādaśāni tu varṣāṇi mahākleśaḥ kṛto mayā
tatkāladṛṣṭadravayānāṃ divyāvāṇīmāyāśruttā/
aḍṣṭapṛārthitā paścāddṛṣṭātvaṃ bhavamāṃ pratāṃ//

śrī vaṭayakṣiṇy uvāca
sādhu sādhu mahāsiddha tvadbhaktiā tu mahātmanā
yatkāyahāritobhadra tatsarvaṃ pradadāmy aham
nāgārjunuvāca [sic]

F. 29v has:

vaṭayakṣiṇy uvāca...
śrīnāgārjuna uvāca...
vaṭayakṣiṇy uvāca...
śālivāhana uvāca ...

F. 32r has:

ratnaghoṣa uvāca...nāgārjuna u[vāca]...

F. 34v has:

ratnaghoṣa uvāca...nāgārjuna uvāca...

F. 35v has:

śrī bhairava uvāca...iti nāgārjunaviracite rasaratnākare traipaṭāmāhrasa
ukta mṛtakhecarabandhaṃ samāptam iti
rasavīryaṃ vipāke ca...

F. 36v has:

...bhiṣagvaraḥ
iti nāgārjuna viracite rasaratnākare guṭikāsatva iti nāgārjunaviracite
rasaratnākare guṭikāsatva__tijalūkājāraṇādirasabandako nāma caturtho
dhyāyaḥ ...
athato raseṃdramaṃgalā[37r]ni yantravidhi śīlāyantram pīṭhayantram
bhūcarayantram ...

Figure 12: MS Jammu Raghunātha 3153, folio 36v.

F. 37v has:

atha pravakṣya sugurūpadeśāyaḥ paṭolākhyasyarasasya ṛddhaḥ

F. 38r has:

iti rāsandre maṅgalaṃ samāptam
atha rasādhikāra ārabhyate hemāhvārajamāvirecana phalair
danūrapatramvanāsammndyothara...

F. 42r-v has:

prasāditaṃ iti nāgārjunavira[42v]cite rasaratnākare lokanāthaḥ
paṭolarasaḥ nāgonādaṃ pāradaṃ melayitvā mande vahnau tane cūrṇe na
sārdham ...

Ends, f. 43v:

dhātrīcitrakavāribhir bahutaraṃ vahnau puṭe
pūrvavadyāvadvāritrobhavedvṛ__ madhubhyāṃ hehayetkṣīrayaḥ
kuṣṭaṣṭādaśahemaṣṇitamaryutyaṅḍūdarāmavaraṇaḥ saṅkhyovinihanti
kāntim atulāṃ dhatte punayovanam|| iti sārasanarasaḥ |||

1.12 Bikaner RORI 4099 (V₃)

Motichand Khajanchi Collection of the Rajasthan Oriental Research Institute, at Bikaner,

Described by Yati and Bishnoi (1990: 166, # 1455/4099).

The details given in the catalogue are:

serial number 1455, accession number 4099. Rasendra-maṅgala,
Nāgārjuna. P[aper]. D[evanāgarī]. Sk. 27.8×14.9[cm.]; 56 [folia];
11 [lines per page]; 30 [letters per line]. C[omplete]. Good
[condition]; [copied in] V.S. 1833. [Scribe:] Prāṇajīvana Tivāḍī.

Figure 13: MS Bikaner RORI 4099, f. 44v.

The MS thus has approximately 1100 granthas.

Begins, f. 1r:

śrīkṛṣṇāya namaḥ/
natvā rasendram śivasaukhyakāraṃ

F. 33r has the Śrīśaila passage:

mātrkayā pratibaddham na gauvyāyatvaritakāmasya //53//
śrīśailaparvvatasthō 'sau siddho nāgārjjuno mahān//
sarvasatvopakārī ca sarva bhāgaṃ guṇānvitah//54//

F. 41v: the main text of the *Rasendramaṅgala* ends and the Ṭippaṇa begins:

sūtakena samāyuktaṃ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ//14//
iti śrīśrīmannāgārjjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale
guṭikāsatvahr̥tijaḷikājāraṇādisabaṃdhanam̐nāma caturtho dhyāyah//
//4// [three missing syllables]
varośābalijinnāgākṣayavyahalarāgagaruḍacaraḥ//

Ff. 44v–46r contain the standard *Rasendramaṅgala* series of drawings of alchemical apparatus. See Fig. 13.

F. 56r, the last folio, ends with has three lines of writing, including:

iti śrīrasendramaṅgalaṭipanakaṃ samāptaṃ// // likhitam idaṃ
pustikaṃ travāḍīprāṇajīvaṇena parārthaṃ// //miti saṃvat 1833 varṣe
poṣavadi 12 somavāsare// //śrīr astuḥ//

The manuscript is dated Somavāsara 12 Poṣavadi, saṃvat 1833, i.e., Monday 20 January 1777 CE.⁶ The scribe was Travāḍī Prāṇajīvaṇa, and he copied the manuscript for another person.

This is the manuscript reported by Śarmā (*RM_{ed}*: xi) as the main source of his edition:

⁶Pillai 1922: 6, 356.

I have compared the published edition with the manuscripts obtained from the Gujarat Āyurveda University, Jamnagar and the the Rajasthan Prācyā Vidyā Pratiṣṭhāna [= RORI] Government Office, Bikaner.... the Bikaner ms. has been mainly followed by me....

The edition of Śarmā (*RM_{ed}*) stops at f. 33 in this manuscript, and does not include the material from the Śrīśaila passage to the end of the manuscript.

2 MSS consulted that are not the *Rasendramaṅgala*

2.1 Bikaner RORI 2945 (V₂)

Rajasthan Oriental Research Institute, Bikaner branch, Government Press Road, Near Ganga Children School Stadium, Bikaner, Rajasthan.

There is a MS catalogued under the title *Rasendramaṅgala* listed by Yati (1984: 328, #2945/14607).

MS in 12 leaves, ff. [1]–12, covering 335 verses on alchemy. Citations from *Rasasāgara*, *Rasārṇava*, *Rasaratnākara*, etc. Marginal initials: *raseṇḍramaṅg*.

Begins, f. 1v,

śivāya namaḥ||
natvā gurum bhairavakanyakāvaṭum
dvaipāyanam siddhamanuṣya lakṣitam

Ends, f. 12v,

iti śrī raseṇḍramaṅgale pāradaśodhanamāranagaṃdhābhrajāraṇādayo
ṣṭasaṃskārādīkathanādhyāyaḥ 1 ||
saṃ 1781 varṣe bhādra vā sudi 6 li. śrīmulatānamadhye||
vā. yuktisuṃdaragaṇinā|| mahimā vijayavācanāya|| śrīḥ|

I.e., copied by Yuktisundaragaṇi in Multān on or about Friday 14th August, 1724. This text in this manuscript is not the same as the *Rasendramaṅgala* ascribed to Siddha Nāgārjuna, in spite of the chapter colophon on f. 12v. It is a compilation of sources on the eight *saṃskāras* and other topics taken from various named sources including late works.

2.2 MS Kāśī BHU C3682 (K)

Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh.

Described by P. V. Sharma and R. S. Tripathi (1984: 129, serial no. 173, accession no. C3682).

Leaves 1–12. 10 lines/page, 39 akṣaras/line of Devanagarī from western India.

With only 12 ff. and 293 granthas, this manuscript covers only about one quarter of the length of the text transmitted by some other MSS (see Table 2).

Incipit, f. 1r:

natvā rasendram śivasaukhyakāraṃ
apārasaṃsārasamudratāraṃ
sarvāthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalam
gramthaṃ kariṣyāmi rasendramaṅgalam ||1||

F. 12r has:

vinaśyati pānāhāravihāraṃ ca suśārthī sevate sadā
rogārttānāṃgu kiṃcit pathyaṃ kārayet||
asya prabhāt sarve rogāḥ nāśaṃ prāptoti niścenaṃ||
iti bhāṣitaṃ||
iti vṛhat paṃcāratnarasa||
iti śrīrasendramaṅgalasamāptaḥ||
śrīrāmo jayati miti mārgaśīrakṛṣṇa 6 saṃvat 1858 liṣkṣataṃ
jyānilacchamaṇa śrīpuramadhye śrīr astu kalyāṇam astu dhanamṭaro
jayati||
udgāre nāga āraśyāta kūrma unmīlanaḥ smṛtaḥ danakalas tu kṣute
jñeyo devadatto vijṛmbhaṇe||
...

I.e., copied by Lakṣmaṇ Jñānī in Śrīpura on 6 kṛṣṇapakṣa of Mārgaśīrṣa, saṃvat 1858, i.e., Saturday 26th December, AD 1801.

Text ends f. 12v:

do uṭaṃka tin lījyai mähāpuṣṭikara so yaho ya napuṃsaka huṃ puruṣa
deṣata bhāga jodra||1||

After a few verses, the text diverges from other MSS of the *Rasendramaṅgala*. The text has common verses with MS Jaipur RORI 4024/4080 (MS J₂).

BHU C3782 = C3682

This manuscript, K, must be the same manuscript as Varanasi BHU C3782 that was described by Rama Shankar Tripathi (1971: #9/6009) and cited in NCC: 23, 168. Described in 1971 by Rama Shankar Tripathi (1971) as being D[evanagari], P[aper], G[ood condition]. Dated saṃvat 1858. C[omplete], 26.2 × 11.6, 12 folios. It is not known whether the correct accession number is C3682 or C3782.

2.3 Jaipur RORI 4024/4080 (J₂)

Rajasthan Oriental Research Institute, Jaipur branch, inside Ramchandra Ji Ka Temple, Opposite Vidhan Sabha Bhawan, Sire Deorhi Bazar Jaipur, Rajasthan.

Described by Vinayasagar and Baldwa (1984: 448, #4024/4080).

Described in the catalogue as:

4024/4080. Rasendra-maṅgala. P[aper]. D[evanāgarī]. Sk.
15 × 8[cm.]; 4 [folia]; 8 [lines per page]; 20 [letters per line].
C[omplete]. Good [condition]; [copied in] 19th century.

MS in 4 leaves, ff. 1–4, covering 44 alchemical and medical verses.
Begins, f. 1r:

śrī gaṇeśāya namaḥ||
natvā rasendram śivasaukhyakāraḥ
apārasaṃsārasamudratāraḥ
sarvārthasiddhipradamukhyamaṅgalaḥ
graṃthaḥ kariṣyāmi rasendramaṅgalaḥ ||1||

Ends, f. 4v:

godhūmānna yan mūtraḥ vijapurāsaṃpamāḥ || 44 ||
iti apathyaviśeṣamūtralakṣaṇaḥ saṃpūrṇaḥ||
śrī dhanvaṃtarāya namaḥ|| cha ... cha

I.e., covers the first few verses of the *Rasendramaṅgala*, but the text diverges after a couple of verses. The text has common verses with MS Varanasi BHU C3682 (MS K).

3 MSS not yet acquired

The following manuscripts have remained elusive for various reasons. Kosambi's Law of Manuscripts states that

The actual use-value of a MS is inversely proportional to the fuss made in lending it.⁷

So perhaps the following manuscripts need not keep us in unbearable suspense.

3.1 Nagaur (N)

Bhattarkiya Granth Bhandar, Nagaur, Rajasthan.

Described by Jain (1978–88: v. 2, p.31), as MS number 322. The manuscript is described as being twelve folios in good condition, on country paper, in the Nāgarī script, and consisting of 1103 granthas and being undated.

The library authorities have not answered my letters and were overtly hostile and insulting when one of my graduate students kindly visited them in 2022.

3.2 Lahore

Private collection of Paṇḍit Rādhākṛṣṇa of Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Described by Rājārāma Śāstrī (ca. 1880: 32, #103).

NCC (23: 168) records a manuscript in the personal library of Paṇḍit Rādhākṛṣṇa of Lahore (d. before 1891). The manuscript is cited from Rājārāma Śāstrī (ca. 1880) in the *Vaidyavidyāpustakasūcī* section. Efforts in 2010 by researchers at the University of Vienna and elsewhere to trace Paṇḍit Rādhākṛṣṇa's manuscripts, including a personal visit by Prof. Tsutomu Yamashita to Balrampur,

⁷Kosambi 1948: 10.

have drawn a blank. The whereabouts of the collection, if it still exists at all, is at present unknown.

4 Conspectus of MSS mentioned in NCC

Manuscripts mentioned in [NCC](#) (vol. 23, 168) and their status in the present overview:

<i>NCC Reference</i>	<i>Biswas #</i>	<i>Known?</i>	<i>Siglum</i>	<i>Notes</i>
BHU 6009	1042	✓		unavailable
Radh 32	0887			collection untraceable
RORI XI 4024	0460	✓	J ₂	RORI Jaipur
RORI XII 2945	0460	✓	V ₂	RORI Udaipur
Saurāṣṭra p. 26	0349	✓	G	Gondal
<i>By Nāgarjuna</i>				
Bikaner 4281	0106	✓	V ₁	Anup
Filliozat 1.146	0794	✓	P	Paris
L. D. Ser. 20 1285		✓	A ₁	Ahmedabad
Nagaur II. 322		✓	N	unavailable
RORI XXVI 1454 (<i>sic</i>)	0460	✓	V ₃	RORI Bikaner
Udaipur SS. 1. 1136	1022	✓	U	Udaipur
<i>With Commentary ṭīkā</i>				
Filliozat 1.146(inc)	0794	✓	P	Paris
L. D. Ser 5. 6498		✓	A ₂	Ahmedabad

Table 1: MSS mentioned in [NCC](#).

5 The illustrated MSS

Manuscripts A₁ (L. D. Inst., Ahmedabad), J₁ (Museum of Indology), B (Asiatic Soc., Bombay) and V₃ (RORI, Bikaner) contain collections of alchemical drawings that are embedded in the ṭippaṇa sections towards the ends of the manuscripts. About thirty pieces of apparatus are sketched in each manuscript, covering three or four folios of each manuscript (see Fig. 14).

These drawings are almost unique in Indian codicology. Scientific illustrations of *any* kind are virtually unknown in the Sanskrit manuscript record. Another manuscript that has illustrations on anything like this scale is the Pune

Figure 14: Sample illustrations from MSS A₁, B, J₁ and V₃.

BORI *Rasaratnākara*.⁸ Prof. Dagmar Wujastyk has discovered many more illustrated manuscripts supporting the *Rasaratnākara* in National Archives of Kathmandu NGMPP collections.

6 Features and stemma

The main complete manuscripts all have approximately the same number of *granthas*, namely 1300, except the Kāśī manuscript K which is a related but different text, and the Goṇḍal MS which seems slightly short.

Manuscripts A₁, A₂, U (to f. 29v), and B have numbered verses. Pa has numbered verses to f. 2v, i.e., adhyāya 1.

A₁, J₁ and B are illustrated.

P and L are known apographs of V₁. They are stemmatically very close to Ko, pointing to a close historical relationship between Ko and V₁.

A₂ is carelessly written, and is not a copy of A₁. A₂ and B record the name of the commentator.

In MS A₁, verse 1, the superscript “*kāarakam*” for transmitted “*dāyakam*” suggests that A₁ was corrected from MS Pa, the only carrier of this reading. The same is the case with inserted “*jarāvināśa*” in verse 8 and “*utpāditau*” in verse 18 (but not of “*sahaja*” in verse 18, which is a semantic gloss). The superscript “*girikarṇī*” at verse 31a points to a reading from a MS other than Pa, perhaps A₂.

MS Ko is an outlier in the stemma and often transmits plausible readings against strange errors in the other MSS. I therefore treat it as the carrier of an earlier stage of the text than the rest of the witnesses, and I have adopted its readings in many cases.

⁸MS Pune BORI 544 of 1892–95 (H. D. Sharma 1939: 257–258, #206).

6.1 Table of MS features

<i>Siglum</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Illus.</i>	<i>Lacuna</i>	<i>Ṭippaṇa</i>	<i>Ṭippaṇa author</i>	<i>Granthas</i>	<i>Script</i>
A ₁	1681	✓	✓	✓		1300	Prṣṭha.
V ₃	1777	✓				1134	
A ₂	1780			✓	Govindabhadra	1336	
K	1801					293	
P (←V ₁)	1899			✓		1164	
G	1939					943	
L (←V ₁)	1984			✓		1287	
B		✓		✓	Govindacandra	1350	Prṣṭha.
U						1113	
J ₁		✓	✓	✓		1450	
Pa			✓	✓		1538	
Ko ₁						1095	
Ko ₂						?	
R						?	
N		?		?	?	1109	

Table 2: Table of MS features.

7 Testimonia

Passages in other works that are the same or similar to the *Rasendramaṅgala* are tabulated in Table 3.

See also the testimonia mentioned by Meulenbeld (HIML: IIB, 716, n. 65–86) for the parallel passages in the *Rasayogasāgara* by Hariprapanna (fl. 1920).⁹ The *Rasendramaṅgala* is quoted or referred to in the *Bhāvaprakāśa*, in Caturbhujā’s commentary on the *Rasahrdaya*, in the *Kūpīpakvaṛasanirmāṇavijñāna*, the *Rasakakṣāpuṭa*, *Rasasindhu*, *Rasatattvavivecana*, *Rasendrasambhava* and Ṭoḍarā’s *Āyurvedasaukhya*.¹⁰

7.1 *Rasaratnākara* of Nityanātha Siddha

Nityanātha Siddha lists the *Dīpikārasamaṅgala* of Nāgārjuna amongst his chief sources.¹¹ This suggests that the Nityanātha was referring to not just the main text of the *Rasendramaṅgala*, but also to the *Ṭippaṇa* commentary that appears in some manuscripts (see Table 2).

⁹Hariprapanna lived in Bombay and compiled his work in the 1920s before its publication in 1927 (HIML: IIA, 701–702).

¹⁰Meulenbeld (HIML: IIA, 717) gives references.

¹¹See Vaiśya 1909: 4; Wujastyk 1984: 77 and note 42. Note that White (1996: 435, n. 235) errs in rejecting the connection between the *Rasaratnākara*’s fifth part, the Siddhakhanda and the *Kakṣāpuṭatantra*. The fact that the former is an abbreviated version of the latter that I noted in my 1984 study was based on a study of the texts themselves, not just their colophons. The colophons do indeed call the work Siddhakhanda the work of Nityanātha Siddha, but the content is a precis of the *Kakṣāpuṭatantra*. One cannot rely on colophons alone.

RM	RRS	RĀ	SDS	AVS	AK
1.8	1.34	1.19	1.34		
1.14	1.23				
1.37ab		10.57a			
1.38ab		10.57c			
1.41		7.31			
1.42		7.52			
1.43		6.83ab			
1.44		7.12			
2.97–98				4.154	
Śrīśaila 72–80		12.364ab–368a			1.23.565ab–568d
Śrīśaila 81–84					18.194–197
Śrīśaila 86					18.200

Table 3: Testimonia. RM=*Rasendramaṅgala*, RRS = *Rasaratnasamuccaya*, RĀ = *Rasārṇava*, SDS = *Sarvadarśanasāṅgraha*, AVS = *Āyurvedasaukhya*, ĀK = *Ānandakanda*. Verses are obviously related; bold indicates identity.

7.2 *Rasaratnasamuccaya* of Vāgbhaṭa

The *Rasaratnasamuccaya* twice lists Nāgārjuna as an authority (see notes above), but does not name the work intended. The list of *siddhas* in which the name appears is reproduced in the commentary on the *Rasendramaṅgala* by Govindacandrabhadra.

7.3 *Rasārṇava*

Several verses of the *Rasendramaṅgala* correspond to the *Rasārṇava*. See table 3.¹²

7.4 *Rasasindhu* and *Rasarājalakṣmī* of Viṭṭhala

H. D. Sharma (1939: 324) noted a citation of the *Rasendramaṅgala* in a manuscript of Viṭṭhala's *Rasasindhu*.¹³ The colophons of this manuscript give confusing information. The work is given two titles at different places, *Rasasindhu* and *Vaidyakaśārasamuccaya*, and the colophons suggest sometimes that the work

¹²See also White 1996: 436, notes 253–266.

¹³MS Pune BORI 634/1895–1902 (H. D. Sharma 1939: 253–4).

is by Mahādeva Paṇḍita, or Galagaṇḍapadāṅkita Mahādeva, or by Viṭṭhala, or that Viṭṭhala is Mahādeva's son.¹⁴

Meulenbeld (HIML: IIA: 772) noted this citation and also that Siddhanāgarjuna is mentioned, and observes that the *Rasasindhu* must have been written after the completion of Viṭṭhala's (aka Viṣṇudeva) other alchemical work, the *Rasarājalakṣmī*.

In discussing the *Rasarājalakṣmī*, Meulenbeld (HIML: IIA: 651) clarified some issues of identity and the name of the author Viṣṇudeva/Viṣṇupaṇḍita/Viṭṭhala and noted that this work too cites a Nāgārjuna.¹⁵ Viṣṇudeva referred to King Bukka I of Vijayanagara (r. 1356–1377), which dates his alchemical treatises to the middle of the fourteenth century.¹⁶

7.5 *Sarvadarśanasāṅgraha* of Sāyaṇa

7.6 *Āyurvedasaukhya* of Ṭodaramalla

B. Dash and Kashyap (1994: 341)

7.7 *The Rasendrakalpadruma*

See also the *Rasendrakalpadruma* that is cited by Rāy (1902–09: v. 2, lxxiv) as having been partly compiled from the "*Rasamaṅgala*," which suggests that manuscripts of the *Rasendramaṅgala* may have been available in Bengal in the mid-seventeenth century (HIML: IIA, 777).

7.8 *Rasayogasāgara* by Hariprapannaji

The *Rasendramaṅgala* was extensively cited in the *Rasayogasāgara* of Hariprapanna in the 1920s.¹⁷

8 Edition

The edition of Śarmā (*RM_{ed}*) is an edition and English translation of the work, done after a meeting with the present author in which I drew the work to his attention as the subject of my research. It is based on consultation of only one or two imperfect manuscripts. The editor misread numerous passages, and as a

¹⁴Raghavan, Kunjunni Raja, Sundaram, et al. (NCC: 23: 151) notes further *Rasasindhu* manuscripts in Nagaur, Jaipur and Bikaner. Further study of these manuscripts may help clarify these confusions.

¹⁵Meulenbeld referred to Sastri (1933: 7417), describing MS serial number 11106 (Burnell 1880: #5492), which is a MS of two *ullāsas* of the *Rasarājalakṣmī* by Viṣṇudeva, son of Paṇḍita Mahādeva.

¹⁶Raghavan, Kunjunni Raja, Sundaram, et al. (NCC: 23: 142–3) treated Viṭṭhala and Viṣṇudeva as different authors, and notes that Viṣṇudeva and his son Rāmeśvarabhaṭṭa both served as personal physicians to King Bukka.

¹⁷Hariprapannaji 1927–30, with citations identified by Meulenbeld (HIML: IIB, 714–17). On the *Rasayogasāgara*, see Meulenbeld (HIML: IIB, 701 f).

Figure 15: Nāgārjuna and Barot. Photo from the shrine room of a private home in Dhank, Gujarat, 1991. Photo by Dominik Wujastyk.

result omits most of the most striking features of the text, including the passages relating Nāgārjuna’s dream of Prajñāpāramitā and his dialogue with King Śālivāhana. The English translation shows a basic understanding of the text, but its language is so poor as to be of negligible scholarly use.

9 Features of the text

The first and main feature of interest is that the work includes a section cast as a dialogue between Nāgārjuna and a Śālivāhana king (see Table 4.). This sets it apart from works such as the *Yogaśataka*, where the name Nāgārjuna appears only in the colophons. In the *Rasendramaṅgala* the relationship of the alchemist Nāgārjuna and the king is integral to the structure of the work as a dialogue. This may indicate that the work is not meant to be by Nāgārjuna himself; alternatively we may consider that the author cast the work partly in dialogue form.¹⁸

¹⁸The unusual dialogue format is also found in the *Kākacāṇḍeśvarīmata*, where the dialogue in paṭala 2 is between Kākacāṇḍeśvarī, Śrīsarvajña, and Bhairava (Rāy 1902–09: v. 2, Sanskrit 42 ff), and in the *Anandakanda* (HIML: IIA, 582 ff), where it is between Bhairava and Bhairavī.

<i>Manuscript</i>	<i>startfolio</i>	<i>endfolio</i>	<i>notes</i>	<i>Saktumiva begun?</i>
A ₁	16v	19v		✓
A ₂	49r	62r		✓
B	15r	18v		✓
G	28r	36v		✓
J ₁	31v	39r		✓
Ko ₁	19v	23r		
Ko ₂	1r	10	whole MS is 10 ff.	
L	49	59	page numbers	✓
P	25r	29v		✓
Pa	14r	17v		
R	28v	36v		✓
U	35v	43v		✓

Table 4: The Śrīśaila passage.

10 The Śrīśaila Passage

Of particular interest in the light of the many stories connecting Nāgārjuna and the king with the building of a *vihāra* is a passage in which Nāgārjuna talks to a Vaṭayakṣa that he has conjured up through his austerity. Nāgārjuna is granted a wish, and asks for the means to perform wonders (L 50:22) and the ascetic discipline of mercury (*rasasādhana*) to conquer death and poverty. He then says that he wishes to make golden the palace apartment of Pārvata, which has thickets and wooded mountains.

The fourth chapter of the work introduces the other feature of the Nāgārjuna story that we have encountered, a mountain, here called Śrīśaila, upon which Nāgārjuna teaches alchemical doctrines to an assembly of fifty listeners, who include Ratnaghōṣa and Śūrasena. At the end, king Śālivāhana declares that he is ready sacrifice all his possessions to the alchemical art, and even his son and Madasundarī.

Other personalities about whom stories are related include Māṇḍavya (usually a mere name in authorities lists) Vasiṣṭha, Ratnaghōṣa, and Nāgabuddhi.

The work is throughout redolent of the Buddhist milieu, and nowhere is this more striking than in the passage where Prajñāpāramitā appears in a dream:¹⁹

प्रज्ञापारमिता निशीथसमये स्वप्ने प्रसादीकृतं ।
नाम्ना तीक्ष्णमुखं रसेन्द्रमङ्गलं श्रीनाथबुधो बुधैः ॥²⁰
तीक्ष्णमुखो नाम रसः सर्वपित्तहरः ।

¹⁹L, p. 12 f., at the beginning of chapter 3.

²⁰In Śārdūlavikrīḍita metre.

During the night, in a dream, the goddess of wisdom Prajñāpāramitā revealed a lucky king of mercury called sharp-mouth, O Śrīnātha, wise with the wise ones.

“Sharp-mouth” is a mercurial that removes all bile.

Index of Manuscripts

(References are to page numbers in this article.)

- Ahmedabad LDI 7753: 5f
Ahmedabad LDI 9442: 3
- Bikaner RORI 4099: 24
- Goṇḍal BP 34: 14
- Jaipur RORI 4024/4080: 26
Jaipur UIOMI 184: 12
Jammu Raghunātha 3153: 8, 19, 21, 23
- Koba GB 19113: 17
Koba GB 26264: 18
- London Wujastyk: 9
- Paris BNF Cordier 1222: 7
Pune BORI 544 of 1892–95: 30
Pune BORI 634/1895–1902: 32
- Varanasi BHU C3682: 27

Abbreviations

- CC Aufrecht, Theodor (1891–1903), *Catalogus Catalogorum, an Alphabetical Register of Works and Authors*, 3 vols. (Leipzig: German Oriental Society).
- HIML Meulenbeld, Gerrit Jan (1999–2002), *A History of Indian Medical Literature*, 5 vols. (Groningen: E. Forsten), ISBN: 9069801248.
- NCC Raghavan, V., Kunjunni Raja, K., Sundaram, C. S., et al. (1949–), *New Catalogus Catalogorum, an Alphabetical Register of Sanskrit and Allied Works and Authors*, 39 vols. (Madras University Sanskrit Series; Madras: University of Madras); v.1: revised edition, 1968.
- RM_{ed} Śarmā, Hari Śaṅkara (2003), *नागार्जुनविरचितम् रसेन्द्र मङ्गलम् ... अनुवादक कविराज हरि शङ्कर शर्मा = Rasendramaṅgalam of Nāgārjuna Edited with Aihore Hindī Vimarśa, Bhāvānuvāda and English Translation and Notes (Chapters 1–4)* (Jaikrishnadas Āyurveda Series, 119; Vārāṇasī: Chaukhambha Orientalia).

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